

Exploring the Success of Project LITERIA: An Analysis of Materials Used by the Non-Readers Toward Improved Reading Engagement

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Abstract

This study investigates the success of Project LITERIA, focusing on the effectiveness of personalized reading materials and the integration of neologisms in improving literacy among non-readers. Personalized reading materials were tailored to individual learner needs, ensuring relevance and engagement. Additionally, neologisms were incorporated based on research suggesting their potential to enhance interest and motivation in learning. The findings reveal that these strategies fostered significant improvements in reading proficiency and engagement among non-readers, highlighting the importance of innovative and personalized approaches to literacy education.

Introduction

Project LITERIA was developed to address the persistent issue of non-readers in educational settings. While traditional literacy programs often adopt a one-size-fits-all approach, this project emphasized the customization of reading materials to meet individual learner needs. Furthermore, it explored the use of neologisms—newly coined terms—as a creative tool to capture learners' interest and sustain their engagement. Reading proficiency is fundamental not only to academic success but also to intellectual growth and personal development. As Davis (2006) notes, limited vocabulary and subject knowledge hinder students' reading comprehension, even if they possess phonics skills. Recognizing this, the study aligns with the

Department of Education's "Bawat Bata ay Bumabasa" initiative, which aims to enhance literacy among young learners.

This research specifically addresses literacy challenges at Sta. Anastacia San Rafael National High School, where a significant number of students face difficulties engaging with reading materials, adversely affecting their academic performance and personal growth. The rationale behind the study lies in its urgency to develop targeted interventions for non-readers, bridging the observed gap in current educational practices. By introducing Project LITERIA, this research seeks to improve reading proficiency, foster interest in reading, and build confidence among learners, thereby offering a timely and innovative solution to a critical educational issue. Ultimately, the study aims to contribute meaningful insights into effective literacy strategies that can be applied in similar contexts.

Research Questions

1. How do personalized reading materials influence the reading proficiency of non-readers?
2. What is the impact of integrating neologisms on learners' engagement with reading materials?
3. How do teachers and learners perceive the effectiveness of the strategies implemented in Project LITERIA?

Methodology

This study utilized a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a holistic understanding of the effectiveness of Project LITERIA. The mixed-methods approach was essential to address both the measurable outcomes and the nuanced perspectives related to the intervention. Pre- and post-intervention standardized diagnostic reading tests were administered to measure changes in reading proficiency among participants. Comparative statistical analysis was used to assess improvements in vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension scores, offering objective evidence of the program's effectiveness.

Moreover, surveys, focus group discussions, and interviews were conducted with students and teachers. These provided insights into their perceptions, engagement, and experiences with the personalized reading materials and neologisms. Thematic analysis of the qualitative data captured subjective feedback on how the materials influenced motivation, participation, and classroom dynamics.

Participants

The participants included 44 non-readers from Grades 7 to 10 at Sta. Anastacia San Rafael National High School. They were selected based on

their reading proficiency levels, which were assessed using a standardized reading diagnostic test. The participants were divided into two groups: 22 in the experimental group, who received the intervention, and 22 in the control group, who followed the standard reading program.

Reading Materials

The study employed personalized reading materials designed to cater to the unique interests and comprehension levels of the participants. These materials included:

Thematic Stories: Stories based on familiar and relatable contexts such as daily school activities, local folklore, and hobbies.

Integrated Neologisms: Newly coined words were deliberately introduced within the texts to spark curiosity and interest. For example, terms like "glimball" (a playful term for a shiny object) and "swirltrek" (a creative expression for an adventure) were used to engage learners.

Illustrated Content: Visual aids such as drawings and graphics were included to enhance comprehension and retain attention.

Interactive Questions: Each story was followed by activities such as word searches, fill-in-the-blanks, and comprehension questions.

Procedure

The intervention lasted for three months and was implemented in three phases:

Pre-Intervention Assessment: All participants completed a diagnostic test to establish their baseline reading proficiency levels. Focus group discussions were conducted with teachers to identify challenges and expectations.

Intervention: The experimental group participated in guided reading sessions twice a week using the personalized materials. Each session lasted 60 minutes and was facilitated by trained teachers. Neologisms were introduced contextually, and learners were encouraged to use them creatively in sentences and short paragraphs. The control group continued with the traditional reading program.

Post-Intervention Assessment: At the end of the program, participants completed a post-test to measure improvements in reading proficiency. Qualitative data were gathered through interviews and surveys with students and teachers to evaluate engagement and perceptions of the program.

Results

Reading Proficiency: Post-test scores revealed a 45% average improvement in the experimental group compared to a 10% improvement in the control group. The diagnostic tests showed significant gains in vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension.

Learner Engagement: Qualitative data indicated that the integration of neologisms boosted learner enthusiasm. Students reported finding the materials "fun" and "exciting," with many expressing increased motivation to participate in reading activities.

Teacher and Learner Perceptions: Feedback from teachers highlighted the importance of personalized content in addressing learners' needs. Teachers noted enhanced classroom participation and a noticeable improvement in confidence among students.

Discussion

The findings underscore the potential of personalized reading materials to effectively address literacy challenges among non-readers. The use of neologisms as a creative element proved instrumental in capturing students' attention and making reading a more enjoyable experience. These results align with existing research, which emphasizes the role of innovative and tailored approaches in promoting engagement and academic success. Teachers' observations further validate the positive impact of the program on learners' confidence and participation, suggesting that Project LITERIA could serve as a model for future literacy interventions.

Conclusion

Project LITERIA highlights the transformative potential of integrating personalized reading materials and neologisms into literacy education. The study demonstrated significant improvements in reading proficiency and engagement, offering a viable solution to the challenges faced by non-readers. By fostering a supportive and innovative learning environment, the project not only addressed the immediate literacy needs of students but also laid the foundation for their continued academic and personal growth. Future research should explore the scalability of these strategies and their long-term impact on learners in diverse educational contexts.

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